

Effect of Ivermectin (Neomac) on Haemato-biochemical profiles against parasitic infections of donkeys

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Introduction

Ivermectin, composed of at least 80% 22,23 dihydroavermectin B_{1a} and < 20% 22, 23 – dihydroavermectin B_{1b} was the first avermectin to be commercialized and was approved for use in animals in 1981(Chabala *et al.*, 1980). Its unprecedented potency and new mode of action quickly made ivermectin the treatment of choice for nematode and arthropod parasitism in cattle, sheep, goats, swine and horses (Campbell and Benz, 1984). Monitoring of haemato-biochemical alteration during parasitic infections in several host-parasite systems is an essential criterion for precisely assessing the drug's efficacy at pre and post anthelmintics treatment (Bhat and Sharma, 1990). The purpose of the study reported here was to evaluate the haemato-biochemical alteration after ivermectin (Neomac inj. INTAS) in helminths infected donkeys.

Materials And Methods

Present study was conducted in Banaskantha district of North Gujarat. Total 40 naturally infected donkeys were selected and were thoroughly screened for helminthic infections, using standard parasitological techniques. These helminthes infected donkeys were administered 1% solution of ivermectin (Neomac inj. INTAS) @ 0.2mg/kg. B.wt. subcutaneously. Blood samples were collected aseptically from jugular vein of donkeys after anthelmintic treatment at 0-day, 21- days and 42-days with the help of vacuette needle 20G. Nine ml of blood was drawn in each vacuette EDTA and vacuette serum clot activator (Greinerbio-one) for obtaining blood and serum sample respectively, labeled and transported to laboratory in icebox.

The haematological investigations viz, haemoglobin (Hb), total erythrocyte count (TEC), total leucocyte count (TLC), packed cell volume (PCV), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and differential

leucocyte count (DLC) were carried out as per method described by Jain (1986).

Various biochemical parameters like total protein, albumin, globulin, glucose, alkaline phosphates (AKP), acid phosphates (ACP), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), creatinine, uric acid, cholesterol, triglyceride, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, Iron, total iron binding capacity (TIBC), zinc and copper were carried out using ready to use kit manufactured by Crest Biosystems, Goa, India. The data were analyzed using student 't' test as described by Snedecor and Cochran (1989).

Results And Discussion

In the present investigation significant increase in Hb, PCV and TEC, non-significant increase in TLC, PCV and lymphocyte and significant decrease in eosinophil and non-significant decrease in ESR and neutrophil and no significant changes in monocyte count were observed after anthelmintic treatment to naturally helminth infested donkeys (Table-1). Similar finding was reported by Bhat and Sharma (1990), Partani et al. (1995), Suchitrasena et al. (2000), Rajkhowa et al. (2004) and Padmaja et al. (2006), that might be due to anthelmintic treatment and expulsion of helminth from GI tract, showing the improvement in hematological parameters indicating the improvement in health status of treated donkeys.

The biochemical profiles in ivermectin treated animals revealed that calcium, phosphorus, glucose, total protein, albumin and globulin increased significantly whereas uric acid, magnesium, zinc, copper, iron and TIBC concentration in serum increased non-significantly at 0 DPT, 21 DPT and 42 DPT (Table-2). The concentration of creatinine, ACP and AKP was decreased non-significantly whereas the levels of triglyceride, AST and ALT were decreased significantly at 0 DPT, 21 DPT and 42 DPT, at the same time concentration of cholesterol was found to be decreased significantly between 0 DPT and 42 DPT, but the decrease in the cholesterol was not significantly different between 21 DPT and 42 DPT. The present finding is in agreement with Specht and Colahan (1988), Yousif et al. (1990), Momin et al. (1992), Varshney and Uppal (1992), Suchitra sena et al. (2000), Galdhar and Roy (2004), Rajkhowa et al. (2004) and Padmaja et al. (2006) in different animals due to helminthic infection.

Concentration of glucose, total protein, albumin, globulin, uric acid, calcium, phosphorus, magnesium, zinc, copper, iron and TIBC was observed to be increased after anthelmintic treatment. This increase could be attributed to elimination of parasite, improvement of appetite and increased gastrointestinal availability and absorption of glucose, protein and various minerals (Radostits et al., 1994 and Rajkhowa et al., 2004). Concentration of serum enzymes like AKP, ACP, AST and ALT was decreased which might be due to elimination of helminth, larvae and toxin liberated by them which would have caused damage to liver and intestinal mucosa of the infected animals. After the anthelmintic treatment the damage would have repaired leading to decline in the level of these enzymes (Radostits et al., 1994).

Table 1: Haematological values in ivermectin (Neomac) treated animals

Sr. No.	Parameters	0 Day Mean \pm SE	21 Day Mean \pm SE	42 Day Mean \pm SE
1.	Hb	7.76 \pm 0.27 ^a	8.88 \pm 0.26 ^b	9.59 \pm 0.23 ^b
2.	TLC	11470 \pm 389.66 ^{ab}	12240 \pm 157.6 ^b	12930 \pm 86.08 ^c
3.	TEC	4.14 \pm 0.14	4.44 \pm 0.093	4.58 \pm 0.079
4.	PCV	29.7 \pm 1.43	32.7 \pm 0.87	34.2 \pm 1.34
5.	Neutrophil	57.4 \pm 2.77 ^a	55.3 \pm 1.48 ^{ab}	51.6 \pm 0.75 ^c
6.	Lymphocyte	35.4 \pm 2.09 ^a	39.6 \pm 1.27 ^{ab}	44.8 \pm 0.797 ^c
7.	Eosinophil	6.8 \pm 1.65 ^a	4.9 \pm 0.69 ^{ab}	3.3 \pm 0.14 ^c
8.	Monocyte	0.4 \pm 0.12	0.2 \pm 0.06	0.3 \pm 0.09
9.	ESR	107.75 \pm 7.93	93.64 \pm 7.46	85.29 \pm 5.70

Table 2: Biochemical values in ivermectin (Neomac) treated animals

Sr. No.	Parameters	0 Day Mean \pm SE	21 Day Mean \pm SE	42 Day Mean \pm SE
1.	Glucose (mg/dl)	48.01 \pm 1.19 ^a	51.54 \pm 1.06 ^b	57.02 \pm 0.92 ^c
2.	Uric acid (mg/dl)	7.06 \pm 0.24	7.09 \pm 0.16	7.12 \pm 0.15
3.	Magnesium (mg/dl)	1.84.0 \pm 0.07	1.94 \pm 0.06	2.04 \pm 0.054
4.	Calcium (mg/dl)	8.26 \pm 0.16 ^a	8.87 \pm 0.12 ^b	9.14 \pm 0.096 ^b
5.	Triglyceride (mg/dl)	352.62 \pm 7.97 ^a	335.19 \pm 7.13 ^b	312.20 \pm 5.81 ^c
6.	Cholesterol (mg/dl)	165.12 \pm 2.66 ^a	151.35 \pm 3.21 ^b	144.24 \pm 3.05 ^b
7.	Phosphorus (mg/dl)	4.21 \pm 0.096 ^a	4.65 \pm 0.082 ^b	4.97 \pm 0.06 ^c
8.	Total Protein (g/dl)	5.93 \pm 0.104 ^a	6.76 \pm 0.12 ^b	7.23 \pm 0.07 ^c
9.	Albumin (g/dl)	3.084 \pm 0.05 ^a	3.46 \pm 0.06 ^b	3.70 \pm 0.03 ^c
10.	Globulin (g/dl)	2.85 \pm 0.059 ^a	3.30 \pm 0.06 ^b	3.52 \pm 0.03 ^c
11.	Creatinine (mg %)	1.90 \pm 0.095	1.75 \pm 0.07	1.65 \pm 0.065
12.	Iron (μ g/dl)	1.46 \pm 2.08	1.49.24 \pm 1.98	1.52.22 \pm 2.15
13.	TIBC (μ g/dl)	438.47 \pm 6.22	448.32 \pm 6.11	455.15 \pm 6.81
14.	ACP (KA unit/ml)	6.82 \pm 0.27	6.19 \pm 0.26	5.78 \pm 0.23
15.	AKP (KA unit/ml)	50.11 \pm 2.76	42.65 \pm 2.78	35.73 \pm 1.94
16.	AST (SGOT) (unit/lit.)	413.75 \pm 7.72 ^a	393.77 \pm 5.48 ^b	341.25 \pm 8.68 ^c

17.	ALT (SGPT) (unit/lit.)	41.44 ± 1.82 ^a	33.72 ± 1.16 ^b	26.76 ± 1.11 ^c
18.	Zinc (mg/dl)	35.61 ± 1.66	36.03 ± 1.60	36.49 ± 1.56
19.	Copper (mg/dl)	98.38 ± 0.73	99.79 ± 0.45	100.35 ± 0.395

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